

Research Data Management for graduates and postdocs.

Information on Good Scientific Practice and on Research Data Management (RDM) can be found on the pages of the Graduate Academy of the OVGU.

[Graduate Academy - Welcome to the Otto-von-Guericke Graduate Academy! \(ovgu.de\)](#)
(accessed on 27.11.2022)

*“The **Graduate Academy** is the central service unit for all doctoral students and postdocs at the Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg. We are providing useful programmes and support in all matters beyond the regular course of study. By expanding and linking the various services at OVGU, we will help insure the best conditions for the successful completion of your doctorate in Magdeburg. We also support your career inside and outside academia after the doctorate.”*

[Graduate Academy - News Portal \(ovgu.de\)](#) (accessed on 27.11.2022)

Funding organizations, such as the German Research Foundation (DFG), expect a statement on the handling of research data when submitting an application, and publishers are also increasingly demanding open accessibility of scientific data in the course of publication.

Starting in 2023, **introduction workshops about research data management** will be increasingly offered - in the best possible cooperation and coordination with the Graduate Academy, i.e. workshops with contents such as what belongs in a data management plan and about tool use, e.g. RDMO for planning and implementation of research data management can be presented (in those workshops).

RDM awareness and as needed!

Possible workshop content:

- Basics of research data management
- DFG Code and research data
- Research data policy of the OVGU
- Creation and content of data management plans
- Archiving and publishing research data
- FAIR Data Principles
- Open Science
- Good scientific practice

Written agreements on access to research data that are made at an early stage help to avoid conflicts, i.e. conflicts that might arise during a research project can be resolved easily.

Recommendation: Data Management Plan!